

Management Prescriptions for Biodiversity Conservation in Western Himalaya: Ghamot National Park, the State Biosphere Reserve, Neelum, Pakistan

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SUMMARY

Management prescriptions, strategies, and management plans are an easily understood set of principles in an accessible form by which a defined area (small or large) may be managed. Biodiversity contributes to our material well-being. We obtained various productive materials from biodiversity, e.g., agricultural materials, food, medicine, industrial raw materials, etc. The biological aim of most prominent concern in Pakistan and AJ&K today is the progressive loss, fragmentation, and degradation of natural and transformed habitats. Rapid Assessment Prioritization of protected area management (RAPPAM) methodology and Participatory Rural Appraisals Surveys (PRAs) were used. Based on the analysis of questionnaires, surveys, field visits, and community discussions, we concluded that communities in and around the study area generally depend on natural resources and are deeply dependent on forest resources. It was concluded that poverty, a lack of basic necessities, and the remoteness of the study area were the most important causes of their reliance on natural resources. Despite its protected status, biodiversity is facing threats from anthropogenic activities, particularly deforestation, unregulated grazing, the extraction of wood, and the extensive extraction of medicinal plants. Major actions for addressing environmental and ecological threats include zoning the study area, reducing anthropogenic disturbance and pressure, enhancing monitoring and management, increasing community engagement, and providing livelihood opportunities. Keeping in view issues and gaps, the present study has been designed to identify different factors and issues that cause threats to the natural resources and to suggest management prescriptions in Ghamot National Park.

Keywords: Management; Biodiversity; Protected area; Conflict; National Park; Ghamot

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INTRODUCTION

Management prescriptions, strategies, and management plans are accessible sets of concepts that may be used to manage a given region (small or big). The management practices are the result of the designing process, and they detail the management strategy, the judgments made, and the basis for these, and the supervision for overall management of a protected area during a set time period (Eurosite, 2005). The

demand for having management strategies is emphasised by the following statement: "If there is no general management plan; preservation, development and use activities in a park will occur in a haphazard basis, often in response to political pressures with little consideration as to the implications for the future. This is likely to result in wasted opportunities and irreparable damage to park reserves and assets (Parr et al., 2008).

Biodiversity improves our material well-being. We received many productive resources from biodiversity, such as agricultural or food materials, medicine, industrial raw materials, and so on. Over 60 wild species have been employed to improve the world's 13 primary crops by delivering insect resistance genes, increased production, and improved nutrition (Rawat & Agarwal, 2015; IUCN, 2012; Mcneely & Miller, 2017). The value of coral reef ecosystem services ranges from more than US\$ 18 million per square kilometer per year for natural hazard management to more than US\$ 100 million for tourist, more than US\$ 5 million for genetic material and bio-prospecting, and up to US\$ 331,800 for fisheries (Worboys, 2011). Pollination by insects (honey bees), bats, and birds is directly or indirectly responsible for the production of at least one-third of the world's food, including 87 of the 113 top food crops. The global economic value of insect pollination is more than US\$ 190 billion per year for the major crops that feed the globe (Rawat & Agarwal, 2015).

Pakistan covers four of the Earth's 10 biomes and three of the world's eight biogeographic regions (IndoMalayan, Palearctic, and Africo Tropical, desert, temperate grassland, tropical seasonal forest and mountain). Approximately two-thirds of the country is mountainous; sudden variations in altitude cause many species to alter over short distances. GoP, 2017; Baig & Al-Subaiee, 2009; Manzoor et al., 2013; Zubair et al., 2019). There are 174 mammal species identified in Pakistan. There are at least three indigenous species among them. In Pakistan, at least 668 bird species have been identified, with 375 of them breeding. A large proportion of Pakistan's bird biodiversity is migratory, with a massive influx of Palaearctic winter migrants, accounting for more than 30% of known species (Ur-Rehman, 2007; Baig & Al-Subaiee, 2009; Khan et al., 2010; Sambrial et al., 2014; Khan et al., 2014; GoP, 2017; Ahsan et al., 2019; Zubair et al., 2019). Pakistan is home to around 177 reptile species, including 14 turtles, 1 crocodile, 90 lizards, and 65 snakes. Thirteen of these are thought to be endemic. These, like other groupings, are a hybrid of Palaearctic, Indo-Malayan, and Ethiopian types (Khan, 2003; Baig & Ahmed, 2007; Khan et al., 2010; Khan, 2016; GoP, 2017). Pakistan has 198 freshwater fish species, including introduced species. This fish fauna is predominantly south Asian, with some west Asian and high Asian elements. There are 29 indigenous species in the area. Among these are the nine species of snow trout (subfamily Schizothoracinae) found in northern alpine rivers. Almost 800 marine fish species have been identified in Pakistan's coastal waters, but no study of their population state or distributional range is known (Arshad, 2011; Pakistan Wetland Programme, 2011; GoP, 2017).

The number of known invertebrates is only a fraction of what is most likely to exist in Pakistan. However, certain taxa are more well-known than others. Among the most well-known are butterflies, or Lepidoptera. The total number of butterfly species is anticipated to approach 400, with considerable rates of endemism in the Satyrids, Lycaenids, and Pierids families. (Faiz, 2019) In the northern mountains alone, eighty

species have been documented, many of which are endemic. Approximately 5,000 species of invertebrates, including insects, have been documented in Pakistan (1,000 species of true bugs, 400 species of butterflies and moths, 110 species of flies and 49 species of termites). Other invertebrates include 109 species of marine worms, over 800 species of mollusks (700 marine mollusks and 100 land snails), and 355 nematode species (Chaudhry et al., 2011; Manzoor et al., 2013; Khan, 2016; GoP, 2017; Faiz, 2019; Ahsan et al., 2019).

There are over 5,700 flowering plant species known, including both native and exotic species. The families having the most species are Composite (649), Poaceae (597), Papilionaceae (439), Brassicaceae (250), and Cyperaceae (202). Among the lower plants, there are at least 189 pteridophytes (ferns and their relatives), comprising 153 Sino-Japanese components and 36 Euro-Siberian components. Pakistan contains four monotypic flowering plant genera (*Douepia*, *Suleimania*, *Spiroseris*, and *Wendelboa*) and around 400 species (7.8%). Sounding (2001), Qamar et al. (2010), Qureshi et al. (2011), Arshad (2011), Ishtiaq et al. (2013), Ahmad et al. (2017), and GoP (2017).

According to Pakistan's existing wildlife law, there are three types of protected areas in Pakistan and AJ&K: national parks, wildlife sanctuaries, and game reserves. Existing wildlife laws do not provide an adequate management framework. The statutes provide authority for protected area management to provincial wildlife departments, but do not delegate authority for adjacent area management to these agencies. As a result, expansion activities in regions next to protected areas frequently clash with biodiversity conservation (Somuncu et al., 2002; Khan, 2003; Baig & Ahmed, 2007; Manzoor et al., 2013; GoAJK, 2018).

Pakistan has made no significant moves toward building a protected areas system, prior to 1966. The World Wildlife Fund evaluated Pakistan's wildlife sources last year at the request of the government, and made recommendations to prevent their degradation (Z. I. Khan, 2003). These included the creation of two huge national parks as well as eight wildlife sanctuaries. This effort was backed up by the formation of the Wildlife Enquiry Committee in 1968, which launched additional proposals for the construction of four National Parks, 18 Wildlife Sanctuaries, and 52 Game Reserves. By 1978, these proposals had far exceeded the existence of four national parks, 44 wildlife sanctuaries, and 65 game reserves (Somuncu et al., 2002). According to the Biodiversity Action Plan for Pakistan, there are 225 Protected Areas in Pakistan, including 14 National Parks, 99 Wildlife Sanctuaries, 96 Game Reserves, and 16 unclassified (private, planned, or suggested). These groups encompass a total of 9,170,121 hectares, or 10.4% of the total land area (Qamar et al., 2008; Somuncu et al., 2009; GoP, 2017). The Wildlife Department of AJK has devised a policy of protected areas for the management and conservation of wildlife and its habitat in response to the suggestion of the Wildlife Inquiry Committee (1968). In AJ&K, there are 18 protected areas, comprising eight national parks (99,191 ha) and twelve game reserves (14,164 ha), totaling 113,355 hectares, or roughly 8.55% of the state's total geographic area (Marwat, 2012; Pakistan CBD, 2014; GoAJK, 2018).

The biological goal of greatest concern in Pakistan and AJ&K today is the progressive loss, fragmentation, and degradation of natural and transformed habitats: the forest area, which is already significantly degraded and fragmented, is undergoing

further loss and degradation; most rangelands are bearing further degradation; and many freshwater and marine ecosystems have already been lost or are threatened with further damage (Muhammad Siddiq Khan & Bhagwat, 2010). Furthermore, the continual degradation of many indigenous species of animals and plants in Pakistan is of major concern today; some species are previously extinct, many are internationally vulnerable, and still more are of national significance. In Pakistan and AJK, the degradation of agro-ecosystems and the growing reduction of domesticated genetic variety are also important issues. (Somuncu et al., 2002; Ali, 2003; Baig & Ahmed, 2007; GoP, 2017; GoAJK, 2018).

The President of Azad Jammu and Kashmir initially listed the AJ&K Wildlife (Protection, Preservation, and Management) Act 2014 as a law in 2010 in order to enhance the legislation pertaining to the protection, preservation, conservation, and management of wildlife in Azad Jammu and Kashmir. It is aimed at promoting the social, economic, cultural, and environmental well-being of local communities in accordance with the goals of international organizations (Qamar et al., 2008; GoAJK, 2018).

Most protected areas in Pakistan lack comprehensive management planning, and where it does exist, it is not well implemented. There is also a trend toward viewing management plans as blueprints rather than adaptable rules that must be constantly updated. The majority of Pakistan's national parks require management planning. Conservation efforts do not match international standards due to a lack of management strategies. Furthermore, wildlife in national parks is more vulnerable to depletion due to a lack of legislative and policy implementation. Attempts have recently been made to address these issues. Many national parks in the country have been shortlisted for global management under a consultative process, including Lal Sahunra National Park (Punjab), Khujrab National Park (NWFP), Kirthar National Park (Sindh), Chiltan Hazar Ganji National Park (Balochistan), Margalla Hills National Park (Islamabad), and Chitral Gol National Park (NWFP) (Khan, 2003; Somuncu et al., 2009).

According to the literature reviewed above, various attempts have been done in AJ&K to maintain and improve biodiversity in order to meet international standards. However, due to a lack of unusual management actions, there are still too many gaps and discrepancies. The protection of environmental biodiversity in protected areas cannot be done without adequate management planning. With concerns and gaps in mind, the current study was conducted to identify various elements and issues that pose risks to natural resources and to recommend management prescriptions in Ghomat National Park.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

STUDY AREA

The study area Ghomat National Park (GNP) is located in the upper Neelum valley which is a part of the inner Himalayas, 170 km north from Muzaffarabad, capital of Azad Jammu and Kashmir. The area of Sharda Range, Sharda Forest division Surgan block compartment no. 16 and 17 with a total area of 27,271 ha (67388 acres) were declared as Game Reserve on 28 July 1982, under the AJK Wildlife Act 1975, and later notified and upgraded to National Park (GNP) under a government notification

no SJ-F-O-02(14)/08-1212/2004 dated April 15, 2004, to ensure the sustainable conservation and management of natural resources of the area by the active participation of local communities. It is managed under the Department of Wildlife & Fisheries Government of AJ&K (Qamar et al., 2005; Qamar et al., 2008; Khan et al., 2010; Baig, 2012; GoAJ&K, 2018).

The study area lies within latitude 35° 24 N and longitude 73° 57 E. at an altitude ranging from 2439–4949 m above sea level. The Park is located on the edge of Surgan Nullah at a distance of about 25 km from Sharda. On its western side lies the Kaghan Valley in NWFP, while on its eastern Indian occupied Jammu & Kashmir. The National Park includes two forest Compartments (16 & 17), of Sharda Forest Range. The access from union council Sharda to Ghomat National Park consists of seven km carpeted road up to Surgan, a small town at the entrance of the Surgan-valley, and a further 16 to 18 km stretch of Jeep able roads from Surgan village to Ghomat village a small settlement at the boundary of park. About 20% of the villages around Park are linked to these points by earthen roads while the rest are approachable through trails and bridle paths Qamar et al., 2005; Qamar et al., 2008; Khan et al., 2010; GoAJ&K, 2018) (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Location, Land cover, Forest cover and topographic map of study area.

TOPOGRAPHY

Mountainous terrain with abrupt and uneven topography, unstable geology, and a snowy and wet climate characterise the research region. The research region is divided into deep valleys and high mountains, and the slopes are extraordinarily steep, approaching 100% at numerous locations hundreds of meters away. Landslides and glacier slides are common phenomena that pose a risk of normal road blockade due to loose rocks, steep slopes, poor land use, reduced vegetation, and high rainfall.

The area is dotted with 25 freshwater springs and tapped by four permanent streams with cold and clear water i.e. Hula Bhaik, Sora, Kali Jander, and Saral which originate from snow melting on mountains peaks join to form Surgan Nullah. When this nullah reaches union council Sharda it makes confluence with Neelum river (Qamar et al., 2005).

CLIMATE

Neelum valley is located in the subtropical highlands climate zone. The climate varies with altitude, but the forest regions in the research area are commonly classified as moist temperate forest, dry temperate forest, sub-alpine scrub, and alpine meadows. Winters are quite cold, with thick snowfall. Summers are quite nice and refreshing. High peaks stay snow-covered until June or even later (glacier), but little rain falls during the summer, while the majority of precipitation falls in the form of snowfall during the winter season. The Pakistan Meteorological Department does not have a meteorological data record for Neelum Valley. The adjacent Muzaffarabad district's meteorology data is used as a sample for the research region. However, because District Muzaffarabad is located at substantially lower altitudes than the research area's lowest point, the results collected cannot be generalized to reflect the Park's climate. Between 2017 and 2019, the average rainfall in Muzaffarabad was 1529.86 mm. The typical monthly daylight temperature in Muzaffarabad ranges from 9 degrees Celsius in January to 29 degrees Celsius in June and July, while the annual day temperature ranges from 18 to 24 degrees Celsius (Qamar et al., 2005).

INDICATOR FLORA

In the Neelum Valley, Qamar et al. (2010) and Ishtiaq et al. (2013) found seven species of gymnosperms, 404 species of angiosperms, 46 species of grasses, 33 species of ferns, and 14 species of fungi. The Sharda forest range's forest working plan gives an excellent overview of the forest types in the research area. *Cedrus deodara*, *Pinus willichiana*, *Abies pindrow*, *Picea smithiana*, *Aesculus indica*, *Viburnum nervosum*, *Sassurea lappa*, and *Pyrus pashia* are important wildlife species. (Qamar et al., 2005; Ishtiaq et al., 2013; Ahmad et al., 2017; Qamar et al., 2010; Ahmad et al., 2017; Qamar et al., 2010; Ahmad et al., 2017).

INDICATOR WILDLIFE SPECIES

The research region is located at the meeting point of three prominent mountain systems: the Hindu Kush, the Karakorum, and the Himalaya. It serves as a natural barrier for environmental zones in these mountain chains. A previous study conducted by Qamar et al (2005) in the study area reported 12 mammals, 35 bird species, including key wildlife species Snow leopard (*Uncia uncia*), Common leopard (*Panthera pardus*), Himalayan Grey Langur (*Semnopithecus ajax*), Himalayan ibex (*Capra ibex*), Musk deer (*Moschus chrysogaster*), Black Bear (*Ursus thibetanus*), Brown Bear (*Ursus acutus*), Black Bear (*Ursus*), (*Lophophorus impejanus*) and Himalayan Griffon Vulture (*Gyps himalayensis*) (Qamar et al., 2005; Nawaz, 2007; Qamar et al., 2008; Khan et al., 2010; Baig, 2012; Khan et al., 2012; Abbas et al., 2014; Ali et al., 2018; Jahangeer et al., 2019; Altaf and Umair, 2022).

SOCIO-ECONOMIC SITUATION

There is no permanent habitation inside the research area. Seven dependent villages rely on the study area's natural resources, having a combined population of about 61, 31, and 734 families, with an average household size of 8.13. (2017 District Census Report) Males outnumber females 49:51. The whole population is Muslim, and the general literacy rate is 17%. Butt, Loan, Sayyed, Mir, Khawaja, Mughal, Minhas, Chaudhry, Swati, Raja, and Kayani are among the various ethnic groupings within the dependant people. Because of the difficult climatic circumstances, the Dependent villages are typically located in wooded areas to allow easy access to grazing grounds and forest resources within the study region People's local economies are dependent on livestock and agriculture. Livestock is kept for domestic use of milk, meat, and wool, but surplus animals and their products are sold to generate cash. This cattle community is nearly fully reliant on the study areas and neighboring area's natural resources.

FIELD SURVEY

The documentation of the respondent information situation assessment, threat assessment surveys were started in May 2020 and completed in April 2022. Rapid Assessment Prioritization of protected area management (RAPPAM) methodology developed by WWF (Ervin, 2003), Participatory Rural Appraisals survey (PRAs) (Sontakki & Venkatesan, 2019) and a structured self-administrated questionnaire was used, the survey was conducted throughout the seasonal settlements inside the study area (Bhaiks) and dependent seven permanent settlements around the study area with the help of field staff provided by wildlife and fisheries department and forest department GoAJ&K. initial information's e.g. household size, number of family members, livestock, source of income, language spoken, education level, family system, land use, etc was collected from the head of the family. Data was also collected through secondary sources such as maps, community discussion, government Departments (Wild life, Forest, Bureau of statistics and Agriculture Department) and NGOs (e.g. Snow Leopard Foundation, Himalayan Wildlife Foundation) already working in the area.

RESULTS

RESPONDENT INFORMATION

In the research region, 280 households (HHs) were visited, and 850 people were interviewed (2020-21). Males outnumbered females (n=680; 80%) by a factor of two. The majority of respondents (n=539; 63.41%) were illiterate. The majority of respondents (n=340; 40%) were farmers, laborers (n=320; 37%), nomads (n=35; 4%), and others such as private job holders (n=20; 2.35%), government employees (n=25; 12.83%), and shopkeepers (n=110; 12%). Except for nomadic Pastoral Gujjar Bakarwal (n=35; 4%), the majority of interviewees were permanent residents of the research region. Except for few seasonal communities known as Bhaiks, no permanent settlements were identified within the study region (local people move into high alpine pastures areas in the summer season for grazing their livestock). Surgan Valley (of which the research area is a part) is fully dependent on the natural

resources of the study region, which includes eight villages with a total population of 6,131 and 734 families with an average household size of 8.13.

SOURCE OF INCOME

A total of 1921 people, men (n=1457; 23.76%) and females (n=465; 7.58%), were interviewed on livelihood production in the research area. Males' main sources of income were work (n=542; 37%), followed by livestock (n=307; 21.07%). Other sources of income include agriculture (n=281; 19.29%), government service (n=145; 9.95%), private jobs (n=113; 7.76%), and business (n=69; 4.74%), whereas livestock (n=258; 55.60%), agriculture (n=164; 35.34%), government service (n=28; 6.03%), and private jobs (n=14; 3.02%) were the major sources of income for women (Table 1).

Table 1. Details of source of income in study area.

Livelihood Sources	Settlements								Total	%
	Surgan	Bakwali	Neelum	Samgam	Samgam Malii	Bagnon	Ghomat	Kundi		
Male										
Govt. Service	33	24	19	17	21	14	9	8	145	9.95
Pvt. service	21	27	7	9	13	31	5	-	113	7.76
Agriculture	47	57	39	33	27	53	14	11	281	19.29
Livestock	27	53	28	45	47	76	18	13	307	21.07
Business	24	19	4	3	5	13	1	-	69	4.74
Labour	79	135	85	62	59	93	20	9	542	37.20
Total	231	315	182	169	172	280	67	41	1457	100
Female										
Govt. Service	13	9	1	1	2	2	-	-	28	6.03
Pvt. service	1	-	-	1	1	10	1	-	14	3.02
Agriculture	31	34	26	18	23	18	8	6	164	35.34
Livestock	42	49	39	24	34	52	11	7	258	55.60
Business	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Labour	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total	87	92	66	44	60	82	20	13	464	100

Monthly average income for males (22,000 PKR/14,125 PKR) and females (13,825 PKR/5250 PKR) in the government and private sectors was higher than in agriculture (11,250 PKR/4,500 PKR), livestock (9000 PKR/5125 PKR), business (11,500 PKR/0), and labour (11,000 PKR/0) (Table 2).

Table 2. Average monthly income from different sources in the settlements in and around the study area.

Livelihood Sources	Settlements and average income (Pakistani rupees)								Average	
	Surgan	Bakwali	Neelum	Samgam	Samgam Malii	Bagnon	Ghomat	Kundi		
Male										
Govt. Service	23,000	22,000	25,000	20,000	23,000	20,000	25,000	18,000	22,000	
Pvt. Service	15,000	15,000	14,000	18,000	15,000	12,000	12,000	12,000	14,125	
Agriculture	12,000	10,000	10,000	8,000	8,000	15,000	15,000	12,000	11,250	
Livestock	10,000	10,000	8,000	10,000	8,000	8,000	8,000	10,000	9,000	
Business	18,000	12,000	10,000	10,000	8,000	12,000	10,000	12,000	11,500	
Labor	12,000	12,000	10,000	10,000	10,000	12,000	10,000	12,000	11,000	
Female										

Livelihood Sources	Settlements and average income (Pakistani rupees)								Average
	Surgan	Bakwali	Neelum	Samgam	Samgam Malii	Bagnon	Ghomat	Kundi	
Govt. Service	18,000	18,000	19,000	18,000	18,000	20,000	-	-	13,875
Pvt. service	8,000	-	-	8,000	8,000	10,000	8,000	-	5,250
Agriculture	3,000	3,000	4,000	5,000	4,000	6,000	5,000	6,000	4,500
Livestock	3,000	3,000	5,000	5,000	6,000	8,000	6,000	6,000	5,125
Business	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Labor	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

A large proportion (1,776; 92.54%) of families in the study region earn between PKR 10,000 and 20,000 per month, with a minor proportion (145; 7.55%) earning more than PKR 20,000 per month (Table 3).

Table 3. Average monthly income of household in study area.

Average income level PKR	Settlements								Total	%
	Surgan	Bakwali	Neelum	Samgam	Samgam Malii	Bagnon	Ghomat	Kundi		
Up to 10,000	101	136	93	88	105	156	38	26	743	38.6
10,000 to 15,000	171	238	135	107	104	190	40	20	1005	52.3
15,000 to 20,000	13	9	1	1	2	2	-	-	28	1.4
20,000 to 25,000.	33	24	19	17	21	14	9	8	145	7.5
25,000 to 35,000	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
35,000 to 50,000	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
50,000 above	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	318	407	248	213	232	362	87	54	1921	100

LAND AND AGRICULTURE

The overall land-use area was 1070 square kilometers. 14 hectares are cultivable (261.8143841 hectare) and uncultivable (808.3341932 hectare). The overall average landholding was 2.83 hectares per family. Crop production was restricted, selective, and seasonal; people grew only a limited variety of crops such as maize and vegetables such as potatoes, tomatoes, and leafy green vegetables. Uncultivated land utilized for grazing and fodder gathering (Table 4).

Table 4. Land ownership and crop cultivation in the study area.

Settlements	Cultivable Area (hectare)	Uncultivable Area (hectare)	Total Area (hectare)	Total HHs	Average area (HHs hectare)	Crop type (cultivable area)	Use of uncultivable area
Surgan	41.3285	57.687932	99.01643	145	0.69	Maize, Vegetable e. g. Potatoes, Beans	Fodder, grazing
Bakwali	53.36791	59.53937	112.9072	151	0.74	Maize, Vegetable e. g. Potatoes, Beans	Fodder
Neelum	33.1842	58.67941	91.86361	95	0.96	Maize, Vegetable e. g. Potatoes, Beans	Fodder

Settlements	Cultivable Area (hectare)	Uncultivable Area (hectare)	Total Area (hectare)	Total HHs	Average area (HHs hectare)	Crop type (cultivable area)	Use of uncultivable area
Samgam	32.6278	50.73746	83.36526	85	0.99	Maize, e.g. Beans	Vegetable Potatoes, Fodder, Grazing
Samgam Malii	26.8104	61.785374	88.59577	82	1.9	Maize, e.g. Beans	Vegetable Potatoes, Fodder
Bagnon	48.08980	173.30155	221.3913	118	1.87	Maize, e.g. Beans	Vegetable Potatoes, Fodder, Grazing
Ghomat	20.1837	185.6495	205.8332	43	4.78	Maize, e.g. Beans	Vegetable Potatoes, Fodder, Grazing
Kundi	6.22204	157.76668	163.9887	15	10.77	Maize, e.g. Beans	Vegetable Potatoes, Fodder, Grazing
	261.814	808.334	1070.14	734	2.83		

LIVESTOCK

The total number of animals in the research area was 3840, comprising goats (n=1090; 28.38%), cattle (n=666; 17.34%), sheep (n=590; 15.36%), and poultry (n=1323; 34.45%). Donkeys (n=99; 2.57%), buffalos (n=40; 1.04%), and horses (n=32; 0.83%) were also counted. The average number of cattle reared per family in all communities was 5.85. People raise cows and goats for milk production, chickens for eggs and meat, and donkeys and horses for food distribution into remote areas, such as Bhaiks. Animals graze mostly in the settlement area or on summer Alpine meadows, with stall feeding performed throughout the winter months (Table 5).

Table 5: Comparison of livestock type reared in study area.

Livestock	Surgan	Bakwali	Neelum	Samgam Mali	Samgam	Bagnon	Ghomat	Kundi	Total
Bullock/Buffalo	13	17	-	4	3	3	-	-	40
Cow	130	156	70	85	73	95	25	32	666
Sheep	80	75	65	70	30	130	80	60	590
Goat	185	110	120	180	80	185	120	110	1090
Donkey	15	8	10	28	7	18	5	8	99
Horse	6	5	-	8	3	8	2	-	32
Poultry	240	273	175	172	68	235	90	70	1323
Total	669	644	440	547	264	674	322	280	3840
Average per HHs	4.3	11.7	5.87	3.6	10.56	4.8143	8.47	15.56	5.85

BASIC FACILITIES

According to the survey, there is only one unsealed jeep able (4x4) tract of 18 km that connects the research region to Surgan community (which remains closed in winter approximately from mid-December to April) and then a 6 kilometer carpeted road up to union council Sharda. A micro hydro power station (MHPS) erected by NGOs was documented in Surgan village, as were other tiny MHPS installed by locals, for example, in Bagnon. Except for Surgan Bakwali and Bagnon villages, all of the

villages in the research area lacked electricity, which was generated by (MHPS) of 5 to 7 kV in Surgan Village. All villages in the research region had access to a public drinking water delivery system that included central water storage. None of the recorded settlement was connected to landline telephone network (Table 6).

Table 6. Comparison of basic facilities recorded in the settlements in study area.

Settlements	Electricity	Road/ Transport type	Fuel Sources	Water Facilities	Communication	Veterinary Services	Sanitation/mu nicipal sewage system/ latrines	Banks/ whole Sale bazaar/ Shops
Surgan	Yes (generated through MHPS)	Carpeted Road All type vehicle	Fuel wood from forest	Yes/pipeli ne	yes phone signals, no post office	No	No/ closed and open latrines are available	No bank and whole sale bazaar, small shops are available
Bakwali	Yes (generated through MHPS)	Unsealed road/4x4 vehicles(clos e from Dec to April due to snow fall)	Fuel wood from forest	Yes/pipeli ne	yes phone signals, no post office	No	No/ closed and open latrines are available	No bank and whole sale bazaar, small shops are available
Neelum	No (but under process)	Unsealed road/4x4 vehicles(clos e from Dec to April due to snow fall)	Fuel wood from forest	Yes/pipeli ne/springs/ nullah	no land line phone, signals and no post office	No	No/ closed and open latrines are available	No bank and whole sale bazaar, small shops are available
Samgam	No (but under process)	Unsealed road/4x4 vehicles(clos e from Dec to April due to snow fall)	Fuel wood from forest	Yes/pipeli ne/springs/ nullah	no land line phone, signals and no post office	No	No/ closed and open latrines are available	No bank and whole sale bazaar, small shops are available
Samgam Mali	No (but under process)	Unsealed road/4x4 vehicles(clos e from Dec to April due to snow fall)	Fuel wood from forest	Yes/pipeli ne/springs/ nullah	no land line phone, signals and no post office	No	No/ closed and open latrines are available	No bank and whole sale bazaar, small shops are available
Bagnon	Yes (generated through MHPS)	Unsealed road/4x4 vehicles(clos e from Dec to April due to snow fall)	Fuel wood from forest	Yes/pipeli ne/springs/ nullah	no land line phone, signals and no post office	No	No/ closed and open latrines are available	No bank and whole sale bazaar, small shops are available
Ghomat	No	Unsealed road/4x4 vehicles(clos e from Dec to April due to snow fall)	Fuel wood from forest	Yes/pipeli ne/springs/ nullah	no land line phone, signals and no post office	No	No/ closed and open latrines are available	No bank and whole sale bazaar, small shops are available
Kundi	No	Unsealed road/4x4 vehicles(clos e from Dec to April due to snow fall)	Fuel wood from forest	Yes/pipeli ne/springs/ nullah	no land line phone, signals and no post office	No	No/ closed and open latrines are available	No bank and whole sale bazaar, small shops are available

ISSUES AND THREATS ASSESSMENT

Grazing and Fodder Collection

Grazing and fodder harvesting were two of the most serious threats to the area's environment. The intensity was classified as high ($L+N >200$), medium ($L+N >100$, but >100), and low ($L+N >100$) based on the number and type (L =local and N =Nomads) of grazers in the region. A large portion of the study area, including Ghomat, Kundi, Alif Rakh, Saral, and Habib Bhaik, Kalejander, Hulla Bhaik, and Saral Nar, falls under high intensity for grazing and fodder collection, while areas of Kamakhodari lake, Rata changh, Sora, Biah gali, and Saral lake, Jor di gali, and Saral Nar, falls under medium intensity. The pasture lands had the most grazing activity, while the forest areas were used for fodder harvesting (Table 7).

Table 7: Recorded grazing and fodder collection intensity at different localities in study area.

Study area/Surrounding	Area Type		Activities		Grazing/Fodder collectors		Intensity		
	Forest	Pastures	Fodder	Grazing	Locals	Nomads	High	Medium	Low
Ghomat	Forest	-	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	High	-	-
Kundi	Forest	-	Yes	Yes	Yes	-	High	-	-
Alif Rakh	-	-	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	High	-	-
Saral	forest	-	Yes	Yes	Yes	-	High	-	-
Habib Bhaik	-	Pastures	-	Yes	Yes	-	High	-	-
Saral Lake	-	Pastures	-	Yes	Yes	-	-	-	low
Kamakhodari lake	-	Pastures	-	Yes	-	Yes	-	Medium	-
Rata changh	Forest	-	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	-	Medium	-
Kamakhodari Nar	-	Pastures	-	-	-	-	-	-	low
Saral Nar	Forest	-	Yes	Yes	Yes	-	High	-	-
Sora	-	-	-	Yes	Yes	Yes	-	Medium	-
Hulla Bhaik	-	Pastures	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	High	-	-
Kalejander	-	Pastures	-	Yes	Yes	Yes	High	-	-
Jor di gali	Forest	-	-	Yes	-	Yes	-	-	low
Biah Gali	-	Pastures	-	Yes	Yes	-	-	Medium	-

Fuel Wood Collection

The communities in and around the study region rely largely on forest resources for fuel wood. Despite the government's restriction on tree cutting, According to the socioeconomic baseline survey and forest department, total wood extraction for fuel wood in the research region was 19849.62 tones (1 tons=907.181 kg) over the one-year period (2020-21), with each village collecting up to 207 tons of wood for fuel wood every month on average. As a result, the annual quantity of fuel wood harvested by each hamlet is 2484 tones. Winter fuel wood harvest is highest (1007.52 tones) compared to summer (646.60 tones) (Table 8).

Table 8: Fuel wood consumption in different seasons in the study area.

Settlement	Fuel wood consumption							Summer+ winter/ per month village (kg)	Annual (kg)
	Summer			Winter					
	No. of HHs	Per day/HHs (kg)	Per Month/HHs (kg)	Monthly/ Total HHs (kg)	Per day/ HHskg)	Per Month/ HHs(kg)	Month HHs (kg)		
Surgan	145	22	660	95700	34	1020	147900	243600	292320
Bakwali	151	23	690	104190	38	1140	172140	276330	331596
Neelum	95	29	870	82650	43	1290	122550	205200	246240
Samgam	85	27	810	68850	44	1320	112200	181050	217260
Samgam Mali	82	28	840	68880	43	1290	105780	174660	209592
Bagnon	118	31	930	109740	47	1410	166380	276120	331344
Ghomat	43	32	960	41280	49	1470	63210	104490	125388
Kundi	15	34	1020	15300	53	1590	23850	39150	469800
Total	734	226	6780	586590	351	10530	91401	1500600	1800720

Timber Collection

Only wood used in the building of household structures, such as doors, windows, walls, and roofs, was noted. During a one-year period (2020-21), total settlements in the research region devoured around 346 mature trees belonging to various plant species such as *A. pindrow*, *P. smithiana*, and *C. deodara* for home structure. Each village had 4-5 dwellings built, with an average of 8-12 mature trees utilized in each construction.

Table 9: Timber harvesting by dependent settlements in study area.

Settlement	Average Timber consumption			Plant Species being used
	Average houses construction annually	No of Trees Required / House Construction	Total trees consumed / Year	
Surgan	7	8	56	<i>P. smithiana</i> , <i>A. pindrow</i> , <i>C. deodara</i>
Bakwali	6	9	54	<i>p. smithiana</i> , <i>A. pindrow</i> , <i>C. deodara</i>
Neelum	5	10	50	<i>P. smithiana</i> , <i>A. pindrow</i> , <i>C. deodara</i>
Samgam	3	11	33	<i>P. smithiana</i> , <i>A. pindrow</i> , <i>C. deodara</i>
Samgam Mali	4	9	36	<i>P. smithiana</i> , <i>A. pindrow</i> , <i>C. deodara</i>
Bagnon	5	12	60	<i>P. smithiana</i> , <i>A. pindrow</i> , <i>C. deodara</i>
Ghomat	3	11	33	<i>P. smithiana</i> , <i>A. pindrow</i> , <i>C. deodara</i>
Kundi	2	12	24	<i>P. smithiana</i> , <i>A. pindrow</i> , <i>C. deodara</i>
Total	35	82	346	

Illegal Extraction of Medicinal Plant

According to surveys and community reports, local extraction of medicinal plants and their reliance on medicinal plants has decreased over time. Furthermore, it has been documented that some communities, particularly people from Chillas and nomads, illegally harvest and sell large quantities of economically important medicinal plants such as *Sassurea lappa* (Kuth), *Sassurea candicans* (Richh Kuth), and Ranunculaceae

(Patrees), During 2020-21 maximum illegal harvesting of economically important medicinal plant species were recorded in Kalejander, Hulla Bhaik, Kamakhodari and Habib Bhaik resulting in degradation of forest habitat, it was also recorded that forest department grants individual licenses to extract medicinal plants from selected areas on a recurring basis. Local people claim that currently there is no proper monitoring system to make sure sustainable extraction of medicinal plant in study area.

Encroachments

Locals and Chillas residents removed significant swaths of forest land for agricultural and housing construction. Major encroachment incidents were documented in Ghomat and Kundi villages, as well as land takeover by Chillas in Hulla, Kamakhodari, and Saral Bhaik.

Human Wildlife Conflict

According to annual reports by wildlife and fisheries department questionnaire survey and community discussion, total livestock losses recorded in between 2018-2021 were 597, maximum (n=186;31.2%) were recorded as killed by common leopard, Followed by snow leopard (n=130;21.8%), Asiatic jackal (n=103;17.3%), Asiatic black bear (n=53;8.88%), leopard cat (n=47;7.87), red fox (n=43;7.2), and least (n=35;5.86%) by Indian wolf. Depredation was highest (n=216;46.93%) on goats and lowest (n=5; 4.48%) on donkeys. Annual economic losses due to livestock depredation were estimated to be USD 135 per household. Furthermore, residents describe crop damage caused by Brown Bears, Asiatic black bears, and primates as a contributing reason to the incidence of human-wildlife conflict. During the study visits and socioeconomic baseline survey, it was estimated that the annual economic losses caused by bear and primates related crop damage amount to USD 35 per household (Table 10).

Table 10: Comparison of livestock depredation by wild predators in the study area.

Predator Type	Livestock Type							Total	Percentage
	Cow/oxen	Goat	Sheep	Donkey	Horse	Dogs	Poultry		
Snow Leopard	13	77	33	1	1	5	-	130	21.8
Common Leopard	18	93	45	4	5	21	-	186	31.2
Leopard Cat	-	3	2	-	-	-	42	47	7.87
Black Bear	3	26	21	-	-	3	-	53	8.88
Asiatic Jackal	-	6	4	-	-	-	93	103	17.3
Indian Wolf	-	11	8	-	-	-	16	35	5.86
Common Red Fox	-	Nil	Nil	-	-	-	43	43	7.2
Total	34	216	113	5	6	29	194	597	100

Illegal Hunting and Poaching of Wildlife Species

Prior to the study area being designated as a protected area, illegal hunting and poaching of wildlife were common, though cases of illegal hunting and poaching have been reduced to some extent. The establishment of Ghamot National Park has reduced illegal hunting and poaching by local communities to some extent. However, it has been documented that some professional hunters continue to practise hunting and poaching. The nomadic (Gujjar Bakarwal) who take their livestock to the pastures during the summer season usually hunt and poach illegally, and intruders from Chillas areas in NWFP usually intrude in the area through Noori top, Saral Bhaik, and Kamakhodari top with modern weapons and equipment, and they hunt and poach important threatened mammals and birds species including *Capra ibex sibirica* (Himalayan Ibex), *Moschus chrysogaster* (Himalayan Musk Deer), *Naemorhedus goral* (Grey Goral), Kaleej Pheasant (*Lophura leucomelana hamiltonii*), Koklas Pheasant (*Pucrasia macrolopha*).

Lack of Community Involvement in Conservation

The villages had minimal responsibility for the administration of the area's resources. The Wildlife Department, WWF Pakistan, and other local CBOs and NGOs, on the other hand, had begun community-based conservation and improvement projects. These projects are insufficient owing to a lack of money and are not being implemented correctly. It was highlighted that a lack of community engagement as a result of a lack of resources was a key challenge in the rapid depletion of the resources.

Lack of Public Education and Awareness

The bulk of society was uninformed of the National Park's ecological importance and its accompanying flora and animals. Local populations had low literacy levels and were uninformed of basic ecological phenomena and their effects on their lives and financial systems. Despite various conservation awareness programmes done by the state government as well as initiatives made by NGOs such as HWF and SLF between 2018 and 2022, local residents and schoolchildren remain unaware of the area's ecological value and related biodiversity.

Lack of Management

Several government and non-government organizations, such as AJKWFD, AJK forest department, and other NGOs functioning in the research region, such as HWF and SLF, were identified through study visits, community discussions, and AJKWFD information. However, various difficulties and deficiencies were identified, such as certain departments being inactive while others lacking finances and resources (Table 11).

Table 11: Recorded existing institution/departments/NGOs responsible for protection and conservation in study area.

Existing institution/Departments/NGOs for park management in study area	Overview of Responsibilities in study area	Issues and Gaps in study area
AJK Wildlife and Fisheries Department	Prepare policies, legislation and regulations of sustainable management of wildlife. Establish and maintain Protected areas Prepare and implement development plans for wildlife Assist state government in implement the biodiversity related Programs Carry out conservation, education and awareness programs on wildlife conservation	Insufficient staff members Lack of funds Lack of monitoring and reporting Lack of staff training Lack of research and planning Lack of advanced equipment
AJK Forest Department	Sustainable management of existing forests. Increasing tree cover through planting Scientific management of rangelands Optimizing the production of forestry goods and services	Lack of monitoring and reporting Lack of enforce legislation and regulation lack of research and planning
AJK- EPA	Monitoring air quality and protection Managing pollution, wastes and hazardous substances Protecting indigenous ecosystems and biological diversity A focus on clean industrial production Provides a No Objection Certificate for construction including inside a protected area	Lack of funds Insufficient staff members Lack of advanced equipment and techniques Lack of enforce legislation and regulation
AJK- Minerals Department	To initiate and expand mining activities enhance the contribution of mineral sector to GDP	Inactive in study area Lack of GIS based mining
AJK- Tourism and Archeology Department	Promotion and development of tourism promoting international and domestic tourism	Lack of staff and funds Lack of staff members and advanced equipment
AJK Agriculture Department	Plays role in managing farm practices provide capacity building and training to local farmers	Inactive in study area Lack of fund Lack of staff tanning
AJK Livestock and Dairy Development Department	Increase the production of livestock.	Inactive in study area Lack of staff, funds and training
AJK District Administration	Maintenance of law & order and protection of life and property of the citizens.	Lack of monitoring and reporting.
Himalayan Wildlife Foundation	working with AJK Fisheries and Wildlife since 2005 in integrated management of natural resources and poverty alleviation	Lack of funds
Snow Leopard Foundation	Working to conserve snow leopards in the region	lack of funds
Local Community Organizations (CBOs and VCCs)	Ensure meaningful participation of the local community in the joint management of valuable ecological resources	Lack of funds and training

Lack of Infrastructure

The state governments have documented that development in the research region has been quite low thus far, with the study area lacking basic infrastructure like as roads and tracks, check stations, rest houses, and hotels.

Table 12: Recorded detail of existing infrastructure, constraints and gaps in study area.

Infrastructure	Available Infrastructure in study area	Constraints and gaps in study area
Roads and Tracks	There is one road which connects Study area to Union council Sharda which remains blocked in winter (mid-December to early April) due to heavy snowfall in the area.	The roads which connect the study area are not paved.
Hotels	4, Present outside the study area, run by locals.	limited number and not meet national standard
Toilets	No	No public toilet in study area
Camping Sites	Informal and unregulated camping sites	Without clear demarcation
Check posts	No	No check post is available
Rest Houses	No	No rest house throughout the study area
Watcher's Huts	One combined forest and AJKWFD	Damaged/ not functional/ inadequate
Information center	No	There is no Information Center in the Park to provide information to tourists, visitors, and students.

DISCUSSION

The study area is located in the union council of Neelum Valley. Sharda, no permanent settlement was recorded inside the study region, however the people who were fully reliant on natural resources were spread in 8 villages with a total population of 61,31. It was recorded that the female population (51:49) was 2% larger than the male population. The average household size was high (8.13). The whole population is separated into castes, with the majority belonging to Mughal (28.53%), Rajput (19.15%), Khawaja (16.21%), and Mir (13.42%), with Hindko and Kashmiri being the predominant languages used for communication in HHs and public places. According to a previous study conducted by Jalil et al. (2016), females outnumber males by 2%, and the average household size was 7.91 people. In Musk deer national park Jalil et al. (2016) reported that caste system plays its important role in resolving matters of marriages, individual conflicts, grass cutting, and compensation for murder in Neelum valley.

The higher female population and average home size might be attributed to limited income sources or the area's remoteness (Jalil et al., 2016). In the studied region, the caste system also signifies social position, political ties, and control and ownership rights over natural resources. According to Ahmad (2000) and Shahbaz and Ali (2009), the residents of Neelum Valley's social standing, political affiliations, and precedents of these dealings take the form of customary laws. According to Awan

and Murtaza (2013), the predominant languages spoken in the Neelum valley region are Hindko, Kashmiri, and Gojari. The majority of the economy in the study region (55.60%) is based on land-based activities such as agriculture, cattle, and forestry. Males' primary sources of income in the research region labor (n=542; 37%) and Agriculture (n=281; 19.29%). Women's primary sources of income were livestock (n=258; 55.60%) and agriculture (n=164; 35.34%). Maize was stated to be the area's main and most cultivable crop. The average yearly agricultural yield per family was 140-220 kg. In all settlements, the average landholding was 2.83 hectares per household. In comparison to agriculture and livestock, the average salary for males and females in the government sector is high (22,000 PKR) (11,250 PKR).

The majority of households in the study region earn less than PKR 20,000 per month. According to Qamar et al. (2008), local residents of Machira national park keep a large number of livestock for agriculture, household, and profitable purposes, which forms an important part of the village economy in this area; additionally, approximately 21% of the total annual income of local people is directly obtained from livestock and its products in the area. According to Afridi et al. (2008), the district of Muzaffarabad required 1.5 million tons of wheat by 2010. The survival of the villages in the MDNP is heavily reliant on livestock. They raise animals for milk, meat, or commerce (Khan et al., 2022).

The main sources of income in Musk deer national park are labour, agriculture, and livestock rising; yearly family income ranged from Rs. 36,000 to 42,000, with an average of Rs. 39,000 (Jalil et al., 2016). The current study's findings are supported by Jalil et al. (2016), who reported that remoteness of the area, a lack of basic necessities, and a lack of jobs in the Musk Deer national park are major causes of local reliance on natural resources. The fact that maize is the major and soul food crop in the study area may be due to variations in altitude. Crop quality is good because people have built water channels up to a length of 3-4 km to irrigate their lands, but crop production is limited due to mountainous areas, small landholdings, and a lack of trained labor in the area. During the field trip, respondents stated that agricultural yields had declined in recent years. The lower output might be attributed to unusually low rainfall during the growing season, a shortage of resources, and a lack of capacity to use modern agriculture practises that can improve agricultural production and efficiency. Ghomat National Park (study area) was established in remote and relatively underdeveloped areas of AJ&K, and as a result, the majority of the people belong to a low-income community. This research backs up previous results by Qamar et al. (2008), Afridi et al. (2010), Jalil et al. (2016), and L. A. Khan et al., (2022), who indicated that the economy in rural areas of Azad Kashmir is dependent on land-based livelihoods. The economy of AJ&K's underdeveloped and isolated districts is poor. According to L. A. Khan et al., (2022), 3.29 percent of respondents had a monthly income of PKRs 25001 or more, while the majority (16.15 percent) had an average monthly income of PKRs 3001-5000 in Musk Deer National Park Neelum valley.

The activities of a nomadic community (Gujjar Bakarwal) that visits the Neelum valley during the summer season, particularly the extraction of medicinal plants and unsustainable grazing practises, have been reported to have a negative impact on the area's biodiversity and natural resources. Degradation, loss of forest

pastures, a lack of veterinary care, training in better animal husbandry methods, and the potential of livestock depredation assaults were among the major issues connected with livestock production. According to Jalil et al. (2016) and L.A Khan et al. (2022), nomads graze their cattle in forest areas and alpine pastures throughout the summer, putting a strain on natural resources and increasing the likelihood of depredation attacks in the Neelum valley. According to Qamar et al. (2008), their illegal activities, such as medicinal plant extraction, posed a threat to the area's natural resources. The overall literacy rate is very low (29%), indicating a lack of educational infrastructure, political unrest, and poverty. However, the surveyed communities in the research region recognise the value of education for both men and women, and they are growing more likely to encourage women to work, particularly in the education and health care sectors. According to Qamar et al. (2008), the literacy rate in Machira National Park is 17.5%, and the majority of the people are poor, which may be due to the remoteness of the area and a lack of basic necessities.

There are reports of low-quality and limited health-care facilities in the area. Even still, seven communities out of eight settlements lack basic health care. Surgan village has only one Basic Health Unit (BHU). Most villages do not even have first aid facilities; this situation worsens during the winter season when the road remains closed due to heavy snowfall. The majority of the population must travel to Sharda, Kel, Athmuqum, or Muzaffarabad for serious medical treatment. Locals in the study area and surrounding areas face a life-threatening challenge due to low standards and limited health care facilities. Lack of health facilities is a severe concern in the Neelum valley, according to Khan et al. (2022), Jalil et al. (2016), Hagler Bailly, (2021), and SLF, (2016). Total wood extraction for fuel wood in the research region was 19849.62 tonnes, with each village collecting up to 207 tons of wood for fuel wood every month on average. The annual amount of fuel wood harvested by each community is 2484 tones. Winter has the highest fuel wood harvest (1007.52 tonnes) as compared to summer (646.60 tons).

According to Shaheen et al. (2011), Hamayun et al. (2013), and Hafeez (2000), fuel-wood utilization is a major source of economic activity in the western Himalayas, accounting for nearly 60% of household energy consumption. The Himalayan region's forests are considered the most depleted and damaged in the world, owing primarily to fuel-wood extraction (Hamayun et al. 2017). The fast growth in population has raised resource demands, notably for natural resources such as deforestation (Butt, 2006; Dar et al., 2012).

Fuelwood is the primary source of cooking and heating in the study area; all of the households in the area use fuelwood for cooking and heating because the locals must survive the harsh winter months by collecting as much fuelwood as possible; there is no alternative source of energy, so they have no choice but to break the law and cut trees in order to collect enough wood to last the winter. These findings support the findings of Shaheen et al. (2011), who reported an annual average fuel wood consumption of 16.642 tons per year, with a per capita consumption of 5.18 kg/day. The high elevation, poverty, easy access to the forest, harsh weather conditions, and lack of alternate fuel resources all contribute to the high levels of fuel wood use in the Neelum valley.

There is just one route connecting the study area to union council Sharda, which is sometimes closed during the winter owing to severe snowfall. The presence of roads, communication networks, and other infrastructure is an indicator of a region's development. The lack of these facilities created a significant opportunity for development of the infrastructure, health, and economic sectors in this region. According to a survey and community discussions, streams and springs are an important source of drinking water and irrigation in the study region. Earlier SLF (2016) surveys concluded that there is a need to establish drinking water testing facilities in the area to ensure that drinking water is tested to determine whether it is safe to drink or not.

The majority of the study region lacks basic amenities, such as sanitation, public bathrooms, power, a landline telephone network, mobile signals, a post office, banks, and wholesale bazaars. Since 2005, the state government and several non-governmental organisations (NGOs) such as the Snow Leopard Foundation (SLF) and the Himalayan Wildlife Foundation (HWF) have collaborated with AJK Fisheries and Wildlife on integrated natural resource management and poverty alleviation in the study area. With funding from the Pakistan Poverty Alleviation Fund, HWF implemented two community institutional development and community physical infrastructure projects in Neelum Valley from 2011 to 2016 (PPAF). Interventions in sanitation, drinking water supply, and irrigation were included.

Poverty in the area was a key contributor to the area's dependency on and abuse of national parks. The principal reasons of poverty in the area include unemployment, lack of awareness, a lack of alternative sources of income, a poor literacy rate, and a lack of access to basic necessities of life. There is a need to integrate local inhabitants' livelihoods with conservation measures through participatory management in such a way that local populations may draw a major share of services from the region.

The research area is rich in natural beauty and biodiversity. It is home not only to iconic species of conservation importance, but also to a reliant human population that is as much a part of the local ecosystem as the plants and wildlife. The degradation of the study area and its resources is linked to the locals and their way of life. The forest environment in and around the research region is degrading owing to deforestation, heavy grazing pressure (including seasonal impact from nomadic herds), unsustainable medicinal plant harvest, and encroachment. Illegal activities such as wood collecting, medicinal plant extraction, encroachment, and hunting were reported as indicators of poor management, monitoring, and protection of the study area and its resources. In the study area, poor implementation of rules and regulations defined by the AJK Wildlife Protection Act 2014 and the Forest Act 1927 was observed. According to locals, some corrupt officials were also involved in illegal activities. The reported exploitation of powers by corrupt officials, as well as a lack of liability and inadequate resources and capacity of community organizations and government departments, particularly the Wildlife Department, was major reasons for ineffective management and monitoring of the national park. Qamar et al. (2005) reported similar issues and threats in the study area. According to Manzoor et al. (2013), the main threats to Pir Lasura National Park's biodiversity are deforestation and grazing. According to L. A. Khan et al., (2022), the population of the MDNP

relies largely on livestock for livelihood and is significantly reliant on natural resources in the Neelum Valley. According to Qamar et al. (2010), natural resources in the Neelum Valley, such as medicinal plants and forests, are under high biotic pressure from human-related activities such as deforestation, overgrazing, overexploitation, and improper plant gathering methods. The current study's findings were supported by M. A. Khan et al. (2014) and Shaheen et al. (2017), who reported that weak management, a lack of monitoring, and poor state government performance were the causes the major issues related to loss of biodiversity in Neelum valley.

Total livestock losses observed between 2018 and 2021 were 597; common leopard (31.2%) was the leading livestock depredator, followed by snow leopard (21.8%), Asiatic jackal (17.3%), Asiatic black bear (8.88%), leopard cat (7.87), and red fox (7.87). (7.2). the goats suffered the most depredations. The annual economic losses caused by black bear and primates-related crop damage are estimated to be USD 35 per household. Human-wildlife conflict was a major threat to wildlife conservation in the study area. Previous research by Abbas et al. (2014) found that human-carnivore conflict was a major conservation issue in Neelum Valley, with several carnivore species suffering greatly as a result of high conflict with local residents. According to Iftikhar et al. (2009), human-carnivore conflict has a significant financial impact on rural areas in the Neelum Valley. L.A. Khan et al (2022) reported goats are ideal leopard prey and the most affected among depredated animals, followed by sheep in MNDP Neelum valley. According to Iftikhar et al. (2009), the common leopard was a prominent predator of live cattle in Machira National Park.

The villages cite cattle depredation attacks as one of the primary reasons for their opposition to the designation of the region as a national park, believing that the designation increased wildlife population and depredation danger. If compensation plans are implemented in the region, their attitude may change. A subsidized livestock and crop insurance system would serve to improve livelihoods, cover economic losses, and aid in the protection of biodiversity in the region. It is stated that all of the identified concerns are the result of a lack of livelihood possibilities, transportation infrastructure, financial resources, and limited alternative revenue creation outlets for residents.

NGOs such as SLF, HWF, and community-based organizations established by the wildlife department in the past for biodiversity conservation in the study area were working closely with government departments to manage and protect forest habitats, conserve populations of sub-mountainous species, mobilize local communities to take an active role in conservation, empower females through vocational training, and raise awareness among locals on the importance of biodiversity conservation. An assessment of government agencies and other organizations in charge of managing resources in the region revealed certain flaws and weaknesses in the existing institutional structure, such as a lack of staff training, capacity building, research planning, and monitoring. The present infrastructure in the study region is insufficient to accommodate the growing number of tourists while also providing effective protection. It is suggested that new infrastructure be built in the study area to meet the increasing visitor needs while also effectively managing security.

MANAGEMENT PRESCRIPTIONS

The most pressing problem is reducing environmental hazards and pressures in the study region. The major efforts taken to address environmental and ecological concerns, institutional challenges, and gaps are outlined here.

Zonation of Study Area

Zoning land units for specific purposes, such as key areas for conservation or recreation activities, is an effective technique for reducing conflicts among diverse users inside protected areas (Herrera-Montes, 2018). The biological and physical characteristics of the study area are extremely diverse. The presence of keystone species issues and threats posed to these species, suitability of areas for key species conservation, local community needs, and visitor activities would all be considered when zoning the study area. The Zonation concept categories various places based on their need for protection. Three key zones have been identified for biodiversity protection and resource sustainability.

Zone I-Core Zone

This zone merits special protection because it contains or supports extremely important natural characteristics and acts as a breeding and nesting habitat for the research area's core animal species. The area must be strictly protected from any damage or disturbances. This zone must contain Kamakhodari, Sora, Ratta Chanj, Biah Gali, Habib Bhaik, Jor Di Gali, Kala Pani, Khula Pani, Utli Gali, Gol Basti, Tarli Gali, and their surrounds. Trails, animal viewing points/hides, and brief interpretive displays are possible. Visiting should be restricted to daylight hours only.

Zone II-Sustainable Development Zone

The area of forest near Ghomat and Kundi villages will be designated as a conservation and sustainable use zone. These lands will be maintained in a sustainable manner to meet the legalised local community requirements (e.g., timber, fuel wood, grazing, or others). This area may be used by migrating wildlife animals with large home ranges, allowing for the preservation of its ecosystems with minimal human interference. This zone will cover the majority of the study area, excluding the core zone. Development activities that aid in park administration are authorized. The park administration reserves the right to change the entry criteria at any moment.

Zone III-Recreational Zone

This space will be made available for ecotourism and other leisure activities. Visitors demand amenities that are required for non-consumptive tourism and recreation. Saral Lake, Kamakhodari Lake, and the regions surrounding Surgan nullah, Hulla Bhaik, Kothiali, and Saral are examples of such locations. The development activities and admittance criteria are subject to predefined criteria established by the park administration from time to time. Motorized access is permitted with park management's permission (Figure 2).

REDUCE ANTHROPOGENIC DISTURBANCE AND PRESSURE

Deforestation, widespread grazing, and illegal extraction of medicinal plants are among the anthropogenic impacts on the study area, as are encroachments, human-wildlife conflict, illegal hunting, and unregulated tourism. The table summarises management measures recommended to mitigate anthropogenic disturbance.

Figure 2: Proposed Zonation map of study area.

Table 13: Anthropogenic disturbance and proposed management prescriptions in the study area.

Description of Anthropogenic disturbance in study area	Proposed Management principles for Anthropogenic disturbance in study area
<p>Deforestation Community exclusively depends on forest wood for cooking, heating and construction in study area.</p>	<p>Set up clear regulations for extraction and sale of trees and fuelwood from the Special-Use Zone Set up clear regulations for use of forest wood by tourism related initiatives and businesses. Strong monitoring and management framework to ensure effective implementation of rules and regulations Provision of alternatives for fuelwood e.g., LPG on subsidized basis and development of hydropower in the long term. Promoting use of alternative construction materials and practices.</p>
<p>Grazing Widespread grazing by locals and nomadic Gujjar Bakarwal livestock results in disturbance and habitat degradation.</p>	<p>Start a Permit system for the Gujjar Bakarwal, to ensure that only families with a historic dependence on summer pastures in Study area can graze their livestock and stay in the study area. Prescribe grazing pattern should be introduced Set up no-go zones for grazing, with strict monitoring, to preserve key wildlife habitat areas against human disturbance, and reduce conflict between wildlife and humans. Livelihood development programs including tourism and increasing agricultural productivity to reduce need for maintain large herd sizes.</p>
<p>Human-Wildlife Conflict Conflict results in heavy economics loss to HHs, and threat to wildlife species</p>	<p>Avoidance of depredation incidents through awareness and capacity building for protective measures. Establishment of a compensation scheme for economic losses Establishment of income generation Subsidized insurance should be introduced Support economic transformation to shift the livelihoods to the extent possible from free grazing to alternatives such as tourism and high productivity agriculture</p>
<p>Illegal removal of Medicinal Plants Results in habitat degradation and exploitation of resources</p>	<p>Establish a community-based management and monitoring system, for the sustainable harvest and sale of medicinal plants. Participation of community in profit from the sale of sustainably harvested medicinal plants, with approximately 30% of the profits to be shared with the government. Promote research and monitoring of commonly used medicinal plants. Provide support to local communities, for processing medicinal plants, and establishing market linkages, to gain maximum profit from limited harvests.</p>

Description of Anthropogenic disturbance in study area	Proposed Management principles for Anthropogenic disturbance in study area
Encroachments Result in deforestation and habitat loss	Identify all illegal settlements/encroachments inside the Study area. Develop resettlement plan for each encroachment. Strengthen monitoring and regulatory framework to detect and punish encroachers in the future
Illegal Hunting	Strict enforcement of laws and regulation Community involvement in monitoring and reporting Heavy fine Create awareness
Unregulated tourism	Establish clear guidelines for use of wood by tourism-based businesses. Establish clear operational guidelines for tourism-based business. Development of Infrastructure and Facilities to Support Tourism Sharing of Revenues from Permitting and Licensing with Local Communities Encouragement and Market Development

ENHANCE MONITORING AND MANAGEMENT

It is suggested that a clear institutional framework be established, with a focus on improving stakeholder coordination, empowering local communities, and establishing monitoring programmes. Key government and community stakeholders must be identified and reinforced in order to execute participatory management of the study area. To improve monitoring and management, establish a park management committee (PMC) with representation from key stakeholders including government departments, establish a park management office (PMO) under the AJKFWD equipped with resources and staff to carry out monitoring and coordinating efforts with local village organizations (VOs)/CBOs, and capacity building of park management staff for monitoring and reporting as well as general administration and a strong grievance redresses mechanism to address community concerns and to strengthen institutional accountability.

INCREASE COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

To benefit from the sustainable use of its natural resources, the local people must be enabled to participate to the management of the study area. Increase community engagement in existing community groups, particularly among women. Strengthen VOs and CBOs to effectively participate in natural resource management, sensitize the local community about major conservation concerns and the importance of sustainable resource utilization, and raise awareness among the local community about benefit sharing and responsibility allocation.

PROVIDE LIVELIHOOD OPPORTUNITIES

Efforts should be made to encourage livelihood diversification and the growth of local and international tourism in order to improve socioeconomic well-being and lessen local reliance on natural resources. Mobilization and enlistment of men and women interested in choosing alternative livelihoods, trainings and workshops to develop skills and capacities for shifting to alternative livelihoods, such as agriculture extension, handicrafts, fish hatcheries, and tourism, as well as funding programmers and awards for alternative livelihood ventures.

ENHANCE INSTITUTIONAL STAFF AND FINANCIAL SUSTAINABILITY OF AJKWFD

A framework must be put in place to assure the AJKWFD's financial viability. For the research area, a funding mechanism in the form of a Wildlife Conservation Fund (WCF), as permitted by law, may be established. The Wildlife Management Advisory Board's Executive Committee, including civil society involvement, can manage the fund. The fund may receive funds from the indicated sources and, as a matter of policy preference, should spend the funds in the region where the revenues are generated. Permits for recreational and subsistence fishing in the study area, entry check-post and fees for the study area, fines collected by the AJKWFD for violations of wildlife rules should be used for study area management and conservation, fees for licencing and extraction of medicinal plants, and taxes on tourism-related activities are among the proposed actions.

Increase staff member of AJKWFD

According to a survey of existing AJKWFD employees and resources allotted for study area preservation, the number of staff members explicitly assigned to the Park is quite low. It is recommended that the department hire more park field officers to improve park management and to increase the capacity of the study area staff, as shown in Table 14.

Table 14: Proposed additional staff of AJKWFD for study area.

Proposed additional Staff	Proposed No. of additional staff	Proposed Responsibilities
Park Manager	1	Ensure Implementation of strategic plans for study area Ensures compliance to applicable legislation and regulations, and relevant standards, guidelines, and procedures Recommends policies and events that would improve study area management Ensures all financial secretarial as well as ensures the preparations of the annual budgets Formulates, executes and supervises plans for wildlife management Supervises enforcement of wildlife legislation by staff Submits the necessary and required information, reports, and records to relevant government departments.
Park	2	Manages projects, activities and programs as assigned by the Park

Proposed additional Staff	Proposed No. of additional staff	Proposed Responsibilities
Rangers		<p>Manager</p> <p>Provides technical guidance to staff on wildlife management</p> <p>Assists researchers and students in data collection and field surveys</p> <p>Supervises the issuance of licenses and camping permits as authorized</p>
Park Supervisors	1	<p>Assists in formulation and development of plans for wildlife management</p> <p>Provides technical guidance to staff on wildlife management and protection</p> <p>Assists researchers in conducting research studies</p> <p>Supervises enforcement of wildlife legislation by field staff</p> <p>Supervises Head Watchers and Watchers in protection activities</p>
Head Watchers	3	<p>Supervises the watchers to conducts daily patrolling in designated areas to check for violations of rules and harm to wildlife</p> <p>Regulates and monitors activities of visitors, local communities and nomadic communities</p> <p>Ensures implementation of rules and regulations especially at trails and hotspots.</p> <p>Submits weekly field activity reports to the Park Supervisors</p>
Watchers	15	<p>Conducts daily patrolling in designated areas to check for violations of rules and harm to wildlife, and reports the violations</p> <p>Regulates and monitors activities of visitors</p> <p>Ensures implementation of rules and regulations especially at trails and camping sites</p> <p>Reports wildlife injuries, diseases and mortalities when observed</p> <p>Surveys and maintains fenced areas</p> <p>Maintains fire lines especially during summer/fire season</p> <p>Submits daily field activity reports to the Head Watchers</p>
Community Mobilizers	3	<p>Works with local communities to raise awareness about the valued resources of Study area.</p> <p>Provides support for development of Village Organizations</p> <p>Organizes regular meetings of the Village Organizations and involve them in conservation and protection</p>
Education Officer	1	<p>Initiates and supervises interactive education and awareness programs for visitors and tourists</p> <p>Provides information to visitors regarding rules and regulations of study area and leads study trip tours</p> <p>Prepares, finalizes and launches education programmes for schools in study area with support of Social Scientist and Community Mobilizers</p> <p>Carries out awareness raising sessions for the local communities with support of Social Scientist and Community Mobilizers</p> <p>Prepares and revises wildlife and protected area information</p>

Proposed additional Staff	Proposed No. of additional staff	Proposed Responsibilities
Office Assistant	1	Communicates with partner institutions and organizations. Maintains communication and coordination among field and office staff. Schedules and organizes official meetings and events Makes arrangements for travels and accommodation of staff Supervises and arranges repair and maintenance, construction and fixture activities at the offices and facilities.
Accountant	1	Prepares financial document and reports Maintains updated knowledge as to all pertinent laws, regulations and standards concerning and affecting accounting procedures Documents financial records/transactions in computer as well as paper records Compiles and analyzes data related to accounts and finance
Driver	2	Provides pick and drop services for staff and guests and has good communication Maintains and operates assigned vehicles Loads, unloads and delivers equipment or other packages at various locations
Peon	2	Carries files and mails between staff as directed Opens and closes office at assigned times

INCREASE ADVANCED EQUIPMENT AND FACILITIES OF AJKWFD

Table 15 summarizes additional equipment and facilities proposed for existing and additional staff in the study area for effective and efficient implementation of protection measures.

Table 15: Proposed facilities and equipment for AJKWFD in study area.

PROPOSED FACILITIES AND EQUIPMENT	PROPOSED NUMBER OF EQUIPMENT AND FACILITIES
VEHICLE (4WD)	04
MOTORBIKES	12
UNIFORMS AND SUITABLE KITS	32
TORCHES, LIFE JACKET AND BINOCULARS,	24
ADVANCED GLOBAL POSITIONING SYSTEMS (GPS)	08
ADVANCED DIGITAL VIDEO CAMERAS	02
AID BOXES	06
ADVANCED COMPUTER	02
SCANNERS AND PRINTER	02

DEVELOP AND IMPROVE INFRASTRUCTURE

Additional infrastructure and amenities should be built in the study area to accommodate the increased tourist demands while also efficiently managing security. Table 16 summarises the existing infrastructure improvements and additional infrastructure suggested for investigation.

Figure 3: Proposed infrastructure for study area.

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis of questionnaires, surveys, field visits, community discussions, and previous studies conducted by government departments and NGOs, it is possible to conclude that communities in and around the study area rely heavily on natural resources, particularly forest resources; this was a shocking situation for conservation

departments and other stakeholders involved in conservation approaches. It was concluded that the most important causes of their reliance on natural resources were poverty, a lack of basic necessities, and the remoteness of the study area. Despite its protected status, biodiversity is under threat from anthropogenic activities such as deforestation, unrestricted grazing, timber extraction, and excessive exploitation of medicinal plants.

Table 16: Proposed additional infrastructure in study area.

Proposed Additional/Existing Infrastructure	Role Of Proposed Infrastructure	Details
Carpeted Roads and Tracks	Will Increase Accessibility and Improve Safety For Visitors, Reduce Habitat Damage (Due To Off-Road Driving), And Reduce Dust Emissions.	Carpeted Main Road From Surgan To Kundi Village Other Tracks As Well.
Entry Gate in Study Area (National Park)	Mark The Entrance Of The National Park	A Large Gate And Sign Board At The Entrance Of The Park.
National Park Entry Check Post	Collect Toll, Perform Security Check Of Vehicles, Provide Information About Rules And Regulations Of The Park	Barrier For Cars, Two Rooms (Guard Room And Information Room), and a Toilet
Information Center	Provide Information To Visitors And Tourists About The Key Biodiversity Values As Well As The Rules And Regulations Of The Park	Two Rooms, Two Toilets And A Small Kitchen
Park Management Office	Provide Office Space And Facilities For Park Staff, Provide Venue For Meetings.	Three Rooms (Two Offices And One Meeting Room), Three Toilets and One Kitchen
Field Office	Manage Protection Activities For Field Staff	Two Rooms and One Toilet
Watchers Hut	Provide Rest Facility For Protection Staff Particularly Watchers	Two Rooms, Two Toilets And A Small Kitchen

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